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Perception Regarding Healthy Lifestyle Practices Among Young Adults in Selected Colleges at Thiruvananthapuram

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ABSTRACT

The present study was aimed to determine the perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices among young adults of Sree Sankara Vidyapeedam College, Nagaroor. Descriptive research approaches with convenient sampling techniques were used for this study. The sample size were 110 young adults in Sree Sankara Vidyapeedam College, Nagaroor. The five point likert scale was used to assess the perception of young adults regarding healthy lifestyle practices. It consists of 5 domains such as eating habits, sleeping pattern, physical activity, health risk behavior and stress management. The institutional research committee granted ethical approval, and individuals gave their informed permission. Data collection took place over the course of one week. The result of the study showed that among 110 young adults most of the subjects (86.4%) had good perception followed by 13.6 % young adults had average perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices. Young people's perceptions of healthy living behaviors were significantly correlated with sociodemographic factors, such as the subjects' year of study ($\chi^2 = 9.43$; p value = 0.003), with a significant difference at $p < 0.01$. The study concluded that majority of young people had good perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices.

Keywords: *Perception, healthy lifestyle practices, young adults*

INTRODUCTION

Background of Study

Young adulthood is a pivotal period for many lifestyle factors becoming established and later affecting health. However, current knowledge on key lifestyle factors among young adults is limited. As young adults even we are not following healthy lifestyle practices most of the time. To make lifestyle interventions better suited to participants' day-to-day practices, it is important to get insight into the target group's perceptions regarding a healthy lifestyle and lifestyle advice.[1]

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that nearly two-thirds of premature deaths, and one-third of the burden of disease in adulthood, are associated with inadequate behaviours or lifestyles that began in youth. Moreover 27–39% of cancer can be prevented by improving dietary habits and physical activity. Most young people are presumed to be healthy but, as per WHO, an estimated 2.6 million young people aged 18-26 years die each year and a much greater number of young people suffer from illnesses which hinder their ability to grow and develop to their full potential.[2]

A cross-sectional study on perceptions regarding healthy lifestyle practices among the adolescents in selected schools of Kerala. Descriptive cross-sectional survey design is applied to assess the lifestyle practices among adolescents. Sampling method was nonprobability convenient sampling criteria framed into the adolescents falls in the age between 12 and 16 years, A total of 100 adolescents fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria in selected schools of Kerala. The result of the study presented that 18% (18) having good lifestyle practices, 27% (27) have average lifestyle practices and 65% (65) have poor lifestyle practices. There is no significant association between social demographic variables and lifestyle

practices.[3,4]

LITERATURE REVIEW

A cross-sectional study on perceived weight status, disease risk and weight loss behaviours among young adults. 86 young adults were analysed from Health and Nutritional Sciences Department, South Dakota State University chi-square analyses and logistic regression used to determine relation among variables. The result of this study showed that the overall 61% of males and 19% of females inaccurately perceived their weight status compare to normal weight, Those who perceived overweight were less likely to perceive high blood pressure as serious (0.14% $p = 0.01$) and type 2 diabetes mellitus as serious (0.21% $p = 0.01$). Among the overweight/ obese, perceived risk of disease given current weight ranged from 3.4% for high blood pressure or heart disease to 17.2% for high cholesterol.[5,6]

150 undergraduate students from Kuwait University participated in a qualitative study on how they see leading a healthy lifestyle and how it affects their health. Information was collected via a lifestyle questionnaire, a standard survey tool by Harris. The result of the study showed that the majority of college students followed a moderate healthy lifestyle, only (50.0%) eat a healthy diet and (48.7%) suffer iron deficiency anemia, while (46.3%) get at least 7 to 9 hours of sleep, (38.7%) suffer from increased body weight and (34.0%) only exercise frequently.[7-9]

A descriptive cross-sectional study of health perception and obesity awareness of nursing students. The sample for the study consists of 502 active registered student nurses in the school of Nursing at a regional University in Australia, from all its classes. The purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between nursing students' health perception and obesity awareness. A student information form,

health perception scale and obesity awareness scale were used to collect data. It was calculated that at least 218 students should be included in the sample, with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence interval. The result of the study showed that among the students, 76.0% stated that there were informed in their classes about obesity and their related diseases, 57.4% said that they also received health related information from social media. The average total score of the obesity awareness scale was 3.14 +/- 0.36, and the average total score of the health perception scale was 38.48 +/- 6.65. [10-13]

A cross-sectional study on perception and practices of healthy lifestyle in late adolescent and its impact on body mass index in the first three years of medical and nursing students, Tanta University. The Sample of the study were used for data collection 524 students. The result of the study showed that 524 medical and nursing students (in grade 1, 2 and 3), their mean age was 19.26 ± 1.17 years. More than one half of students were rural residents (55.5%). Women made up around two-thirds (67.9%). The majority of pupils (60.7%) were of normal weight, with a minority being underweight (1.9%) and obese (6.1%). [14-18]

PROBLEM STATEMENT

A descriptive study on perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices among young adults in selected college at Thiruvananthapuram District.

Objectives

- Assess the perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices among young adults.
- Find out the association between perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices with selected socio demographic variables.

Assumption

Young people may have varying perceptions towards healthy lifestyle practices.

Materials and Methods Research Design

Nonexperimental research design.

Setting of the Study

The study was conducted at Sree Sankara Vidyapeedam college, Nagaroor.

Sample and Sampling Technique Sample

The sample for the present study includes students of Sree Sankara Vidyapeedam college who were between the age group of 18 to 25years

Sample Size

The sample size was calculated from the findings of previous study conducted by E. Isabagh M Italia, Soliman E Fatma, Hassan A Lulah on perception and practices of healthy lifestyle in young adult and its impact on the body mass index and found that proportional score, $p = 52.4\%$.

The sample size was calculated by the formula, $N = 4pq/d^2$

$$\begin{aligned} P &= 52.4\% \\ q &= 100 - p = 47.6\% \\ d &= 20\% \quad \text{of} \quad p = 9.52 \quad d^2 = 90.6304 \\ N &= (4 \times 52.4 \times 47.6) / 90.6304 \\ &= 110.08 \end{aligned}$$

So, the sample size was fixed at $n = 110$

Sampling Technique

Criteria for sample selection Inclusion criteria

- Those who are between the age group of 18-25 years
- Those who are present during the time of data collection.

Exclusion criteria

- Those who are not willing to participate in the study

- Those who are not present at the time of data collection.

Tools and Technique

The tools consist of following section:

Section1: Socio demographic performa

The socio demographic performa consist of 11 items such as age, gender, religion, year of study, marital status, type of family, occupation of father, occupation of mother, area of residence, monthly income of family and health problem.

Section 2: Five pointlikert scale

The five pointlikert scale was used to assess perception of young adults regarding healthy lifestyle practices. It consists of 5 domains suchas eating habits, sleeping pattern, physical activity, health risk behavior and stress management. There are positive and negative statements, each statement has 5 options named strongly agree, agree, uncertain, disagree, strongly disagree. The scoring of each statement ranges from 1-5. The interpretation is as follows:

- Poor perception (26-60)
- Average perception (61-95)
- Good perception (96-130)

Content Validity

Validity refers to the degree to which an instrument measures, what it is supposed to measure. To determine the content validity, it refers to the adequacy of the sampling of the domain being studied.

The tool was given for content validity to 9 nursing experts and 1 statistician. The experts' suggestions were accepted, and modifications were made in the tool.

Reliability of the Tool

The degree of consistency with which an instrument measures the attribute it is intended to assess is known as its reliability.

After validation the tool was subjected to test for its reliability the five point likert scale was administered to 11 selected second semester students studying at Sree Gokulam Nursing College. Using Cronbach's alpha, the tool's dependability was determined. The tool was determined to be dependable ($r=0.79$).

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

1. The Sree Gokulam Medical College and Research Foundation's institutional ethical committee granted ethical clearance.
2. Setting permission obtained from head of the institution, Sree Sankara Vidhyapeedam College Nagaroor.
3. Written informed consent was obtained from the study participants prior to the study after explaining the objectives and ensuring the confidentiality of data collected.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

The data collected process involves precise, systematic, gathering of information relevant to the research purpose, questions or hypothesis of a study.

To conduct research study in selected college, at Sree Sankara Vidhyapeedam Nagaroor, formal permission was obtained from the college authority and ethical committee of Sree Gokulam Nursing College.

The investigators introduced themselves to the subjects, topic was explained to them and confidentiality was assured. An informed consent was taken from all subjects individually after explaining the objectives and purpose of the study. After obtaining permission from the subjects, socio demographic performa and five pointlikert scale were administered and data were collected. The overall experience was good.

Plan for Data Analysis

The process of arranging, classifying, and examining data so that a research issue may be addressed or significant conclusions can be made is known as analysis. It is the systematic organization and synthesis of research data and testing of research hypothesis using that data.

It was planned to use descriptive and inferential statistics on the basis of objectives and assumptions of the study. SPSS Version 20 was used by investigators to analyse the data. The data will be analysed in terms of descriptive (frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation) and inferential statistics (chi-square test).

Section-1: Description of sample characteristics

Demographic data containing sample characteristics would be analysed by descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage).

Section-2: Perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices

Perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices were analyzed by descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation)

Section-3: Association between level of perception and selected socio-demographic variables

Association between perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices among young adults with selected socio-demographic variables were analysed by using inferential statistics (chi-square test).

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Section 1: Distribution of socio- demographic variables

[n=110]

Fig. 1: Distribution of samples according to age.

Fig. 2: Distribution of samples according to gender.

Fig. 3: Distribution of samples according to religion.

Fig. 4: Distribution of samples according to year of study.

Fig. 5: Distribution of sample according to marital status.

Fig. 6: Distribution of samples according to type of family

Fig. 7: Distribution of samples according to occupation of father.

Fig. 8: Distribution of samples according to occupation of mother.

Fig. 9: Distribution of samples according to area of residence.

Fig. 10: Distribution of samples according to health problems

Section- 2: Distribution of perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices among young adults

Table 1

n=110

Level of perception	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)	Mean	SD
Average	15	13.6	2.8636	0.34474
Good	95	86.4		

Table 2

n=110

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Eating habits	110	20.163	2.244 37
Sleeping pattern	110	25.7182	2.59898
Physical activity	110	23.4182	2.97815
Health risk behaviour	110	17.1818	2.97754
Stress management	110	17.4364	1.89895
Total Perception	110	103.8000	8.01238

Table 3: Association between perception of healthy lifestyle practices with selected demographic variables among young adults.

n=110

Year of Study	Level of perception		Chi – square valued f	Level of significance (p value)
	Average	Good		
1 st Year	13	42		
2 nd Year	2	46	9.43	2
3 rd Year	0	7		0.003**

Nursing Implication

The study's conclusions have a number of ramifications for research, education

administration, and nursing practice.

Nursing Research

The study can be replicated on a large scale in different settings and different categories of students.

A much more standardized scale can be developed so the attitude of the students towards the perception as a whole can be assessed.

Abstracts of the study can be published in nursing journals, so that further research will be possible based on present studies.

Nursing Education

A self-awareness classes for the students can be conducted to improve the knowledge regarding the perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices.

Nursing Service

Modified best practice learning environment scale can be used to identify the perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices among young adults.

Nursing Administration

To counsel the students regarding the importance of engaging in healthy lifestyle behaviours such as eating a nutritious diet, regular physical activities, adequate sleep, reducing stress and avoidance of substance use.

Recommendations

In the light of the study the following recommendations are put forth.

- The study can be replicated on a large scale involving many colleges and community settings.
- A similar study can be replicated to generalize finding

Limitations

- The study was limited to sample size of 110.
- The study was limited to only one college in Thiruvananthapuram.
- The response of samples was restricted within 5 domains

CONCLUSIONS

The study was to access the perception regarding healthy lifestyle practices among young adults in Sree Shankara Vidya Peedam College. The sample size was 110 and was conducted in Sree Shankara Vidya Peedam College. Here we used descriptive study design.

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